

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Object;

Yusuf Paper Analysis For The Value Of Friendship In One Piece Manga Volume 80-85
Written By Eiichiro Oda

Background and Analysis

Abstrak : The meaning of this study is to dissect the values of friendship recorded in the manga "One Piece" written by Eiichiro Oda which is very popular among children and adults around the world. Beginning information for this study is the manga "One Piece" by Eiichiro Oda. The data format is the format of the important elements that make up the manga "One Piece" by Eiichiro Oda which includes characters and features, settings, plots, themes, and the value of friendship contained in the manga. The research process was carried out using data accumulation and elaboration techniques. Data were obtained by reading and recording.

Conclusion : From this, we can conclude that Eiichiro Oda's "One Piece" manga has many values and messages of friendship. Manga and comics are tools that have a function to convey a message. As a medium, comic messages are generally clear and pleasant. For that, manga media or books can be a source of learning. Comics represent the important value of friendship for everyone. Something that is conveyed by the author but is conveyed through comics as a means of entertainment. Comic or manga can make something serious and complex seems more lively and fun.

Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Qustions:

1) Is it Available data or information to answer it,

Yes there is, there is some data that can be used as data to answer it

2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

Yes, some data are obtained from documentation, scientific methods, and direct observations both through comics and related articles some data is also through the comics themselves, then from several online articles and old journals as references.

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),

Yes, this fulfills the originality that has been identified through several previous studies and some of the data is obtained through one's own mind and also the data contained in the original source, namely the One Piece comic.

4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,

No, this does not make a theoretical contribution to the development of science because what is discussed here is friendship and friendship has nothing to do with science because friendship is more focused on the feelings and emotions felt by 2 people.

5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,

No, this journal does not discuss controversial issues that are currently happening, but rather discusses the importance of friendship for a human being

6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public

No, this problem does not require an immediate answer and solution because this friendship problem must be formed through time and trust in order for a friendship to occur

7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

Yes, the issues posed are within the limits of the author's interests and abilities

8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

The shift that occurs in the events in the journal is when a pirate captain wants to invite a friend who is trapped by a family wedding held by his family and the sea emperor. In this case, the main character tries desperately to persuade and fights against all the problems that come his way in order to get his best friend back.

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

What is obtained from this research is their understanding of the importance of friendship in the world of work, science, and society in the future why it is like that because a friendship between 2 people will make life easier because they can share their problems, help each other, and positive friendships will produce positive results too, for example, the Google Company was founded by two friends, Larry Page and Sergey Brinn they met at Stanford University in 1995 and then founded Google in 1998. Not only they have many influential people out there who are successful with his best friend.

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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